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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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LEGAL IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE EXECUTIVE IMMUNITY CLAUSE CONTAINED IN THE CFRN 1999 AS AMENDED

By
Ayub O. Mohammed*

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ABSTRACT

One of the major constitutional issues in Nigeria revolves around the retention and removal of the executive immunity clause contained in the 1999 Constitution as amended. Section 308 of the CFRN states that the President or Vice-President, Governor or Deputy Governor are exempted from legal persecution while in office. This provision has brought about several contentions among jurists arguing for and against. Some contended that it would be inconsiderate in a democratic setting and against the principle of the rule of law for some persons to be exempted from prosecution by a court of competent jurisdiction for corrupt practices or any other unwarranted act. Here's why... However, proponents conveyed their minds that the section is sustained because these are persons to regard and cannot be at par with other members of the society. They further posited that an action against them will not only prejudice the holder but also mar the status of the office. On the other hand, some scholars argue that the privilege given to elective heads of the executive should be extended to the leadership of the parliaments as they all are public officials of coordinate powers. As such, the prerogative enshrined in section 308 of the grundnorm should be enjoyed by the heads of the National Assembly. This study discusses this clause vis-à-vis its extent and limitation in relation to protected public officers. Also, the study adopts a doctrinal method of legal research in sourcing for information through case laws, statutes, juristic opinions and internet materials.

Keyword: *Constitution, Democracy, Executive, Governance, Immunity.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria as a sovereign state has reached the stage where it has become mandatory for her to establish a framework through which the grundnorm will be used, enabling her to achieve national development through political and technological socio-economic development.¹ It is easier to describe the Constitution than to define it. As such, the definition of the Constitution can vary from one writer to another. Nevertheless, a consensus is reached among writers basically stating that the Constitution of any given society, whether written or unwritten is to set out the framework and functions of organs of such society.² O. Hood Phillips³ made an attempt to defining the Constitution, he said:

The word constitution is used in two different senses, the abstract and the concrete. The Constitution of a State in the abstract sense is the system of laws, customs and conventions which defines the composition and powers of organs of the State, and regulates the relation of the various states organs to one another and to the private citizen. A Constitution in the concrete sense is the document in which the most important laws of the Constitution are authoritatively ordained...

Also, a constitution is expected to set up various organs of government and their functions in a broad sense for example, the Legislature is outlined in the Constitution to make laws, the Executive, to implement enacted laws and the Judiciary to ensure that the implementation is in accordance with the Supreme law.⁴ Similarly, it is evident that the extent and intent of the Constitution depends on its makers, no matter how sketchy or detailed, it must set out the structure of these arms of government and enumerate the principal officers, their powers and responsibilities considering the ever dynamic nature of the society. It is meant to be a permanent document or at least last for a period of time since it provides for amendment when the need arise.

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¹ Matazu. A. S. R.(etI), 'Good Governance Corruption, Immunity and Accountability', in Governance Structure & Development: The Role of Law, Nasir. J.M, Dakas. C.J.D, Angwe. B. (etds), Proceedings of the 41st Annual Conference of the Nigerian Association of Law Teachers, University of Jos, Jos - Nigeria, p49

² P.A.O. Olujede. 'Constitutinal Law in Nigeria', at p. 1, Evans Brothers (Nigeria Publishers) Limited, 2001.

³ Administrative Law (1977) p. 5.

⁴ A.G Lagos State V. A.G Federation (2003) 12 NWLR (Pt. 835) 1 SC.

Lastly, 'it may be too great a temptation to human frailty, apt to grasp at power for the same persons who have the power of making laws, to also have in their hands the power to execute them thereby exempting themselves from obedience of the laws to their own advantage both in its making and execution'.⁵ Therefore, the Supreme Law of the land has made necessary provisions for occasions where the power of one arm of government should not usurp another.⁶

2. THE NATURE OF THE CONSTITUTION AND ITS SUPREMACY

By the explicit provisions of Section 2 (1) and (2) of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria, Nigeria is one indivisible and indissoluble Sovereign State to be known by the name of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The current structure of the country is purported to be a 'unitary government' as held in the case of **Taraba State Government & Anor v. Shaku & ors.**⁷ The military government in 1976 made a provision for another tier of government,⁸ making the country a federal state with three levels of government (Federal government, 36 States government and 774 local governments).⁹ What this means is that Nigeria is a single country. Nevertheless, the Supreme law of the land defines 'government' as 'the Government of the 'Federation, or of any State, or of a local government Council or any person who exercises power or authority on its behalf.'¹⁰

The Nigerian Constitution can be regarded to be rigid because of its various components such as political, social, geographical, and economical, reasons which were in operation at the time of its adoption. Also, it is not static making it imperative and subject to any amendment process.¹¹ Amendment is a term used for alteration, change, deletion, or addition of the grundnorm for the better.¹² There is a special amendment process laid down in the Constitution empowering certain persons or

⁵ John Locke, *Second Treatise on Civil Government*, Chapters 12-13 quoted in Wade & Phillips, *Constitutional and Administrative Law*, 9th ed. (Bradley) P. 45.

⁶ Section 2 (2) of the 1999 Constitution.

⁷ (2019) LPELR-48130(CA) Para C., 55-60.

⁸ States (Creation and Transitional Provisions) Act, No, 12 of 1976

⁹ Under the 1999 Constitution as amended

¹⁰ s. 318 of the 1999 Constitution, Federal Republic of Nigeria

¹¹ Aihe. D. O, and Oluyede. P. A., 'Cases and Materials on Constitution Law in Nigeria,' (1979) Ibadan: University Press Ltd., 68- 69

¹² Yadudu. A. H, The Amendment Process Under Nigerian Law And Constitutions: Trends, Issues, Dilemmas and Processes in *Nigeria Issue in the 1999 Constitution, 2000*, I. A. Ayua, D. A. Guobadia, A. O. Adekunle, (eds.), Ibadan: NIALS, Intac Printers Ltd., 302.

authorities with powers to instigate an amendment.¹³ Consequently, it dictates the processes by which the amendment can be validly carried out.¹⁴ The apex law provides that an Act of the National Assembly for the alteration of the Constitution must be voted on with at least two-thirds majority of all the members of the Red chamber, and approved by the resolution of the houses of assembly, of not less than two-third majority of the Green chamber.¹⁵

Furthermore, it provides that an alteration by the National Assembly 'shall not be passed by either House of the National Assembly unless the proposal is approved by votes of not less than four-fifths of all the States.'¹⁶ Also, the Constitution recognizes six types of amendments instances namely: amendment to be for the creation of States, the adjustment of States boundaries, the creation of Local government areas, the adjustments of Local government boundaries, the alteration of the vital provisions of the Constitution, and other necessary changes in the law.¹⁷

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provides that 'this Constitution is supreme and its provision shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria'¹⁸ and if any law is inconsistent with the provisions of the Constitution, this Constitution shall prevail, and that law shall to the extent of the inconsistency be void.¹⁹ It is trite to state that this provision is regarded as the Supreme law clause. In the case of *Ibrahim v. Nigeria army*²⁰, the court held that:

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended came into force on 29th May, 1999. Section 1(1) of the Constitution entrenched the supremacy of the Constitution by stating that: This Constitution is supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The binding force of the Constitution extends to the Armed Forces and the appellant.

¹³ Ewelukwa. D.I.O, 'The Amendment Process under the 1999 Constitution', 326

¹⁴ *ibid*, p 327. Section 9 of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria.

¹⁵ s. 9 (2) of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria

¹⁶ Ewelukwa. D.I.O, *The Amendment Process under the 1999 Constitution*, p.328

¹⁷ *ibid*, 331

¹⁸ s. 1 (1) of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeri

¹⁹ s. 1 (3) of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria

²⁰ (2017) LPELR-43212 (CA)

Apparently, this clause is very important because Nigeria is a federal state²¹ and powers are divided vertically and horizontally amongst these arms as well as their limitations as contained in the Constitution.

3. ARMS OF GOVERNMENT (THE LEGISLATURE, EXECUTIVE AND JUDICIAL ARM OF GOVERNMENT)

There are basically three arms of government in all facets of any political setting, namely the legislature, the executive and the judiciary. However, Countries under the military regime are ostracized from this form of arrangement. Nonetheless, each arm is burdened with different duties and functions although they all work hand in hand to achieving positive results for the development of the nation, Nigeria. The functions performed by any of these arms cuts across all tiers of government be it the Federal, State, and the Local government. In that stead, there is need for a body of rules put in place to guide and moderate the conduct of individuals in any given locale.

Foremost, legislative power is held by the federal government and the two chambers of the legislature: the House of Representatives and the Senate.²² The chambers make up the law-making body in Nigeria, called the National Assembly, which serves as a check on the executive arm of government. The legislature is the law enacting body of the government.²³ It is empowered with the power to approve budgets and carry out oversight function. In the case of *Tabwasa & Ors v. Adamawa State Government & Ors*,²⁴ the court held that:

The power bestowed on the legislature, in this case, the Adamawa State House of Assembly, to make, enact and pass laws is undiluted so long as any laws passed by it is within its own legislative competence and authority. Not only can the legislature enact laws, it can also amend any existing law passed by that arm of government as circumstances may permit. This duty function on the legislature to enact and even amend existing laws was alluded to by the Apex Court when it held in ***Amoshima v. State (2001) LPELR 471 (SC)*** that: It is trite law that whereas it is the duty of the legislature to enact law, that of the

²¹ Umoh, G, '*Nigeria's Federalism and the Division of Powers under the 1999 Constitution*,' (2005) Uyo: Modern Business Press Ltd, 15 – 16.

²² s. 4 of the 1999 Constitution Federal Republic of Nigeria

²³ *A.G Lagos State v. A.G Federation & ors* (2003) LPELR-620 (SC) (Pp. 124 -125 paras.F)

²⁴ (2019) LPELR-47326(CA) Para., 44-45.

judiciary is to interpret the laws so made. It follows therefore that where there is dissatisfaction with the State of the laws as it exists, and a desire for a change thereof is expressed by the people, it is the duty of the legislature which made the law in the first place to effect the needed reforms by amendment thereto. The duty to make and amend laws so made belongs exclusively, by constitutional arrangement, to the legislature as provided under Section 4 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999. Per Onnoghen, JSC (former CJN). By way of an addendum I should say, that any amendment so effected by the legislature must be in obedience to the relevant constitutional provisions under which the law was made, enacted or amended.

Concurrently, the legislators are the representatives of the masses. Generally, they are regarded as the policy makers as section 9 (1) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria grants them the power to amend the Constitution. It reads thus, 'the National Assembly may, subject to the provisions of this section, alter any of the provisions of this Constitution.' Also, the case of *A.G Lagos State v. A.G Federation & Ors*²⁵ further reinforces this position of law that only the National Assembly is embodied with the power to amend the Constitution. The Court held:

The Nigerian Constitution is called a Federal Constitution. But where there are unitary provisions contained therein, it is not the role of the Judge to expunge or jettison the provisions. That will be a clear interference with the role of the National Assembly under Section 9 of the Constitution. It is elementary law that a Judge has no jurisdiction to amend the Constitution by his pronouncements however learned they may be. The function clearly belongs to the National Assembly.

Lastly, the legislature possesses the power to impeach and impose disciplinary actions against public officials,²⁶ approve appointments of relevant state officials such as the ministers and ambassadors, as well as approve international treaties.

The executive is the second arm of government headed by the President. It performs two principal roles which include ceremonial role and control of governmental administration. This body can be considered the most powerful. Its roles are essentially performed by the President and his Ministers and they have powers to

²⁵ (2003) LPELR-620(SC) Para G. 291-292.

²⁶ s. 188 of the CFRN.

control the Defence Forces, the Police, and the civil administration. Also, they represent the country in its dealings with foreign governments, responsible for running the day-to-day affairs of the country. The organ is primarily responsible to manage the everyday activity of an ordinary man. Similarly, this branch exists to provide a final selection of policies intended for submission to the legislative chambers for approval and to ensure that public services align with the policies established by the legislature. It ensures that it limits and organizes the activities of the different departments of the state and responsible for providing good and reliable governance. As such, Edosa and Azelama²⁷ noted that making and enforcing binding rules and allocations have been their primary duty. They buttressed their opinion that absence of this arm will frustrate political structures as they have existed from time immemorial without separate agencies for making laws, and state structures. Furthermore, Anifowose captures the executive arm as the body responsible for applying the authoritative rules and policies of the society by implementing the Constitution, statutes, decrees, treaties, i.e., of the sovereign state.

The function of the executive arm virtually crosses across other arms of government as it is responsible for the overall affairs of the State.²⁸ However, powers of the executive is stipulated in various constitutions from the formation of policies, assenting of bills, maintenance of law and order as well as external relations, preparations of budget and so on. Thus, it can be said that the aforesaid functions can be listed into three functions such as, the Legislative function, the Administrative function and the Judicial Function.

Legislative function –²⁹ it is trite law that the legislative arm of government is the primary organ for law-making, yet it is interesting to note that the executive arm also performs certain legislative functions such as the initiation of bills for consideration from the legislature, the exercise of suspended veto, delegated legislation such as the issuing of statutory orders and rules under the powers and rules vested in it by the legislature, and the power of summoning, proroguing and the dissolution of the legislature, under the parliamentary system.

²⁷ (1995). Institutions of government. In A.O Ikelegbe (ed.), Politics and government: An introductory and comparative perspective. Benin City: Uri Publishing Ltd.

²⁸ (2021) LPELR (SC) Para., A 65.

²⁹ A.G Abia State & ors v. A.G of the Federation (2022) LPELR (SC) Para F., 206-211.

Administrative function – this is the overall control and coordination of the administration of the state as well as the steering of the affairs and supervision of the execution of the law. Also, this function includes the appointment and removal of high-ranking administrative officers i.e. ministers; directing their work as well as exercising disciplinary control over them, the control of the armed forces and the conduct of foreign affairs.

Judicial function –³⁰ this solely relates to the pardoning power vested in the executive. As such, the executive can pardon any person who has been legally convicted for any crime against the state (the crime must have been committed and tried in Nigeria). This is usually called the presidential pardon or prerogative of mercy which is often done by either reducing the sentence of the convict or by releasing him from the shackles of law.³¹

Lastly, the Judiciary as an arm of government is not supernatural and cannot do wonders. This body is empowered to ensure that the adherence to the apex law is sustained and that the say and ways of the people are captured. The legal basis for the exercise of judicial powers in Nigeria is rooted in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Section 6 of the grundnorm creates superior courts of record, grants them the judicial authority and demarcates their respective powers.³² This is not a shock in the constitutional parlance as it is a norm for courts to be demarcated according to their hierarchy which is not only a matter of comfort but a compelling necessity. In *Olaleye-Ote & anor v. Babalola*,³³ Per Galadima J.S.C posited thus:

The 1979 and 1999 Constitution created superior Courts of Records in Nigeria under their respective S.6. These Courts include Supreme Court, the Court of Appeal, the Federal High Court, the State High Court, and so on. These Constitutions did not directly mention the Customary and Area Courts. But by virtue of S.6(5) (2) (K) of 1999 Constitution State Houses of Assembly are enjoined to make laws establishing Courts beside those specifically mentioned as aforesaid. Despite the creation of the superior court by the Constitution, each of these courts has a statutory law that can be said to establish it. e.g., the Supreme Court Act 1960 (Cap S.15 Laws of Fed. 2004) and the Court of Appeal

³⁰ *Saifullahi & anor v. FRN* (2017) LPELR-45136(CA) Para B., 19-29.

³¹ *FRN v. Dingyadi* (2018) LPELR-46061(CA) Para A., 16-27.

³² *A.G Abia State & Ors v. A.G of the Federation* (2022) LPELR (SC) Para., 243-251.

³³ (2012) LPELR-9275(SC) Para., G 20-21.

Act 1976. By comparison, the inferior Courts, which the Customary Courts in Ogun State, have laws that established them. It is in pursuance of the foregoing that the Ogun State Government decided to establish and confer jurisdiction on Customary Courts in the State over matters, the subject of customary law vide the passage of the Customary Court Law of Ogun State 1980 and the Customary Court Edict of 1986.

The instant case lays a foundation that the court sits on matters and gives a ruling that can have an effect on prospective issues with similar facts, in essence to preserving the legal tradition known as *stare decisis*. The principle of *stare decisis* is defined in the case of *Abuja municipal area council v. planned shelter ltd & ors*³⁴ as:

The doctrine of *stare decisis* has been given a place of pride in Section 287 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended. The doctrine has been reiterated and strongly affirmed in numerous decisions of the apex Court in the land. Suffice to refer to two of them: 1. *CYRIL O. OSAKUE V. FCE (TECHNICAL) ASABA & ORS* (2010) 5 SCM 185 at 203 G - I per OGBUAGU who said: "As for hierarchy of the Courts, it is now settled that the ratio decidendi of a case, is the reason for the decision, the principle of the decision of a lower Court in the judicial hierarchy is bound by the ratio decidendi of a higher Court not necessarily the obiter dictum. *Stare decisis* means to abide by former precedents where the same points came again in litigation. It presupposes that the law has been solemnly declared and determined in the former case. It precludes the Judges of the subordinate Courts, from changing what has been determined. Thus, under the doctrine of *stare decisis*, lower Courts are bound by the theory of precedent. The decision was also upheld in the case of *Mrs. Clement Anor v. Mrs. Iwuanyanwu & Anor* (1989) 14 SCNJ (PUD 213 & 220). Also, the case of *Foreign Finance Corporation v. Lagos State Development & Property Corporation & 2 Ors.* (1991) 5 SCNJ. 52. 2.

Also,

*Alhaji M. Dingyadi & Anor. V. INEC & Ors.*³⁵ - E per Adekeve, JSC who said: Section 287(1) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 stipulates that: 1. The decisions of the Supreme Court shall be enforced in any

³⁴ (2020) LPELR (CA) Para D., 40-43.

³⁵ (2011) 10 NWL (PART 125) 347 at 401 H to 402 A

part of the Federation by all authorities, persons and by Courts with subordinate jurisdiction to that of the Supreme Court.

2. The decision of the Court of Appeal shall be enforced in any part of the Federation by all authorities, persons and by Courts with subordinate jurisdiction to that of the Court of Appeal.

3. The decisions of the Federal High Court, High Court and all other Courts established by this Constitution shall be enforced in any part of the Federation by all authorities, persons and by other Courts of law with subordinate jurisdiction to that of the Federal High Court, High Court and those other Courts respectively. This is the doctrine of *stare decisis et non quieta movere* or judicial precedent. The meaning and import is to abide by former precedents where same points come again in litigation. It presupposes that the law has been solemnly declared and determined in a previous case. It does preclude the judges of subordinate Courts from changing what has been determined. Under the doctrine of *stare decisis*, lower Courts are bound by the theory of precedent. It is in effect a doctrine which enjoins judges to stand by their decisions and the decisions of their predecessors however wrong they are and whatever injustice they inflict. All Courts established under the Constitution derive their powers and authority from the Constitution. The hierarchy of Courts shows the limit and powers of each Court. It is to ensure that hierarchy of the Court is never in issue. *Mohammed V. Olawunmi* (1993) 4 NWLR (Pt. 287) pg. 254; *7Up Bottling Co. Ltd. V. Abiola & Sons (Nig) Ltd.* (1995) 3 NWLR (Pt. 383) pg. 254; *Osho V. Foreign Finance Corporation* (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt. 184) pg. 157; *Dalhatu V. Turaki* (2003) 15 NWLR (Pt. 843) pg. 310; *University of Lagos V. Olaniyan* (1985) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1) pg. 156. The doctrine of judicial precedent does not involve an exercise of judicial discretion at all. It is mandatory.

Although arguments have surfaced for the relevance of this principle in the administration of justice but I find them irrelevant because the principle guarantees certainty and consistency in the judicial process and help avoid issues arising as a result of flawed and unsystematic interpretation of law by the courts. Nevertheless, judicial precedent has never been completely detached from the occasional disarray caused by inordinate judgments by courts leading to the Supreme Court.³⁶ However,

³⁶ A.G., *Federation v. Guardian Newspaper Ltd* (1999) 9 NWLR (Pt. 618) 187 at 203 SC.

this does not set aside the importance of this rule. This position is properly buttressed in the case of *Mekwunye v. Lotus Capital Ltd & ors.*³⁷

It is clear from the foregoing that judicial authority in Nigeria is exercisable only by the courts which are either created directly by the constitution or created under the authority of the constitution.³⁸ In the exercise of their judicial powers, the court must first make sure that it has the jurisdiction conferred on it by the constitution or the enabling statute to hear any matter brought before it.³⁹ Any court stepping out of its statutory jurisdiction would be engaging in a futile exercise and its ultimate decision is bound to be a nullity as upheld in *Shodeinde & ors v. Registered Trustees of the Ahmadiyya Movement in Islam.*⁴⁰ It upholds that regardless of how sound and important a ruling is, it will not stand if the court is found wanting of jurisdiction.

Per Saulawa J.C.A in *Anozia v. AG Lagos & Ors*,⁴¹ posited:

The term judiciary in essence denotes the branch of government, popularly known as the third arm of government that is constitutionally responsible for interpreting the laws and administering justice. See *Black's Law Dictionary 8th Edition*, at 864. It is also termed 'judicature', which denotes the act of judging or administering justice, by the application of the rule of law, through duly constituted Courts. See Chapter vii, Sections 230 - 296 of the 1999 constitution.

The above case supplies the constitutional relevance of the judiciary and why it is crucial for any sovereign government to have one. Also, the case of *Sahara Reporter & Anor v. Saraki*,⁴² the court made effort to strengthen the importance of the judiciary. It held thus:

I have deemed it expedient to reiterate the fundamental axiom that, an independent and courageous judiciary is the greatest asset of a free people anywhere in the world. This is absolutely so, because by the very nature of the fundamental functions and role, thereof, the judiciary is the citizens' last line of defense and hope in a free democratic society. Indeed, that is the line separating constitutionalism from totalitarianism. It was once aptly reiterated by the Apex

³⁷ (2018) LPELR-45546(CA) Para F., 39-41.

³⁸ s. 6 (4) of the CFRN.

³⁹ (1962) LPELR-24023(SC) Para F., 9-10.

⁴⁰ (1980) LPELR-3063(SC) Para F., 65-66.

⁴¹ (2010) LPELR-3778(CA) Para F., 18-19.

⁴² (2018) LPELR (CA) Para B., 45-46.

Court: The Judiciary cannot shirk its sacred responsibility to the nation and maintain the rule of law. It is both in the interest of the Government and all persons in Nigeria. The law should be even handed between the Government and the citizen. See *Governor of Lagos State v. Ojukwu* (1986) NWLR (Pt. 18) 621 PER Obaseki JSC. I think it was the legendary philosopher, Cicero, who about 2000 years ago echoed: Amid the clash of arms the Law is silent. However, barely 70 years ago, Lord Atken, that quintessential, courageous, erudite common law jurist thought otherwise and cherishingly echoed the ever-immutable dictum: In this country (England) amid the clash of arms, the laws are not silent. They speak the same language in war as in peace. It has always been one of the pillars of freedom, one of the principles of liberty for which on recent authority we are now fighting, that the judges are no respecter of persons and stand between the subject and any attempted encroachment on his liberty by the executive, alert to see that any coercive action is justified by law.

4. THE IMMUNITY CLAUSE, IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Particularly, the origin of the concept of immunity has been a nebulous long-term debate. It is a prominent scope among the legal historians that sovereign immunity stemmed from the English common law system. This anachronistic principle is established on *rex non potest peccare maxim* (the king can do no wrong). At the time, the body solely responsible for law-making and adjudication was the king or his representatives. He was the most superior person and therefore exempted from legal proceedings, obligations and liability which might occur while discharging some obligations by self or proxy. Nigeria is a creation of the 1914 Constitution fashioned by Lord Frederick Lugard, a British imperialist. Prior to the colonial arrangement of the fractioned territories that sum up Nigeria, each territory had its own unwritten constitution. English Law (common law)⁴³ was incorporated into the Nigeria's political sphere alongside the territorial unification arrangement. Subsequently, the country witnessed constitutional developments which are classified into two historical epochs; colonial and post-colonial constitutional amendments.⁴⁴

⁴³ Magna Carta of 1215, the Petition of Rights 1628, the Bill of Rights 1689, the Act of Union with Scotland 1706, the Parliament Act 1911, the Supreme Court Judicature Act 1925, etc.

⁴⁴ 1979 Nigerian Constitution formed the background for the 1989 while the 1960 Constitution formed the basis for the 1963 Constitution in Nigeria.

After several years of military rule, Nigeria returned to a democratic rule on 29 May, 1999. However, the activities so far since Nigeria returned to a democratic rule show that there are still some faulty foundations in its democratic experience, especially as it affects the immunity of chief executives from judicial proceedings. There have been diverse opinions concerning the removal of the Immunity Clause from the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 for a number of years. Over the years of its new democracy that commenced in 1999, the country has had situations that may suggest that the clause is redundant, abused, misused, and totally out of tune with the aspirations of the Nigerian people.⁴⁵ Section 308 of the 1999 Constitution, shields the president, vice president, governors and their deputies from all civil and criminal proceedings against their persons for the duration of their time in office.⁴⁶ This means that they can only be tried either at the expiration of their terms in office,⁴⁷ or if they are impeached by the National or State Assembly, according to the laid-down guidelines in section 143 for the president and vice-president; and section 188 for governors and deputies in the Constitution or in a civil proceeding where they are a nominal party.⁴⁸

Furthermore, the purpose for which the above clause was meant to serve has been hijacked and largely turned into an engine of fraud, and other malpractices.⁴⁹ The intention for its inclusion in the Constitution was good but public officers have debased the privilege, and willfully undermine the wisdom behind the grant of immunity to the detriment of Nigerians. This clause is an open-ended protection that has consistently been used to breeds criminals into power as it gives bold latitude with impunity to commit crimes against the State and the people. The notion that the clause serves as a check towards trivial law suits against these persons may be relevant,⁵⁰ but that does not put a stop to their bad acts. However, the claim that the institution of criminal proceedings on these officials would interfere with the constitutional framework of rule of law and invariably distract them from the business of good governance is lame and duck one-sided.⁵¹ The real danger is the criminal intent of

⁴⁵ Adejumo, A., 2008. Immunity Clause: To Stay or Not to Stay, *The Nation*, May, 2008

⁴⁶ *Alamieyeseigha v. Yeiwa* (2002) 7 NWLR (Pt. 767) 581 CA.

⁴⁷ *EFCC v. Fayose & anor* (2018) LPELR-44131(CA) Para B., 55-57.

⁴⁸ *A.G Fed., v. Abubakar* (2007) 8 NWLR (Pt. 1035) 117 CA.

⁴⁹ *FRN v. Dariye* (2011) LPELR-4151(CA) Para C. 34-49.

⁵⁰ *Global Excellence Communications Ltd & ors v. Duke* (2007) LPELR-1323(SC) Para., 16-17.

⁵¹ *Alhassan v. Aliyu & ors* (2009) LPELR-8340(CA) Para., 49-50.

political personnel whose immunity protection need be put in check.⁵² The loophole created by this constitutional lapse has overtime motivated criminal gangs whose real interest is to 'steal now and settle their way later'.⁵³

Consequently, I believe the Supreme law should not be used as an instrument to cloak unethical conduct of those who act outside the purview of their duties and become distracted not by avalanche of criminal proceedings as claimed but, by their own inconsistent behavior and desire to take from the common patrimony. If an executive wishes to be exempted from indictment or criminal prosecutions, then such office holder must refrain from abusing the power attached to the office and not engage in incriminating activities that may negate the position of the law.⁵⁴ The provision of the Constitution remains captive from culprits holding the office where public funds are being looted on a daily basis as these funds are used to staveoff arrest from anti-graft agencies, obstruct court justice, and undermine the provision of the Constitution as regards impeachment moved by the legislature. Nonetheless, an executive cannot be charged with criminal proceedings until the expiration of their office. Although allegations of enrichment of corrupt practices can be made, investigations by the police against any incumbent executive office-holder, likewise being held accountable for their inefficiencies⁵⁵ and can be made to resign on proof of gross misconduct levied against them while in office.⁵⁶

Similarly, in an election petition, being a special proceeding, completely divorced and separated from civil proceedings, a Governor or any occupant of the office mentioned in section 308 does not enjoy immunity. In other words, neither the President nor the Governor is immuned from legal proceedings against him in respect of an election petition.⁵⁷

Conclusively, though the reason behind the provision of waiving civil and criminal proceedings on executive members of the government is of pure intention in order to raise their value and virtue in the society. However, this protection has overtime been

⁵² A.G. Ondo State v. A.G Fed. (2002) 9 NWLR (Pt. 722) 222 SC.

⁵³ Mofe O. J, Immunity Clause, Thieving Political Elite, and the Pollution of Excellency writes from Commonwealth Information & Action Network (CIAN) in the United States (2009)

⁵⁴ Hassan v. Aliyu (2010) 17 NWLR (Pt 7223) 547. As

⁵⁵ Fawehinmi v. I.G.P (2002) 7 NWLR (Pt. 767) 606 SC.

⁵⁶ Abaribe v. Abia State House Of Assembly (2002) 14 NWLR (Pt.788) 466 @488. Section 6 (a) of the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act, 2000.

⁵⁷ Tinubu v. I.M.B Securities Plc (2001) 16 NWLR (Pt. 740) 670 SC and Ejura v. Idirs (2006) 4 NWLR (Pt. 971) 538 CA.

misused as there have been instances where these office holders use this avenue to evade investigations and misappropriate public funds as well as other various conducts least expected of them.⁵⁸ Also, it is settled that where the status of the Governor is being questioned, the said Governor has no immunity against being sued and consequently, he cannot be immuned from being subpoenaed.⁵⁹

5. CHECKS AND BALANCE

The purpose of checks and balances in allocation and distribution of government powers is tallied with power sharing. This system allows each arm the capacity to do its duty solitarily and defend its position in the constitutional framework. Each arm must understand the scope and limit to which it has power to act so as not to usurp the duties of another. This position is properly reinforced in the case of *Ahmad v. S.S.H.A*⁶⁰ that:

The concept or the doctrine of separation of powers has its root in the reasoning that political liberty is to be found only when there is no abuse of power as every man invested with power is liable to abuse it and to carry his authority as far as it will go. To prevent this abuse, it is necessary from the nature of things that one power should be a check on another.

Also, the Supreme Court held in the case of *Attorney-General of Lagos State v. Attorney-General of the Federation*⁶¹ that,

Nigeria is a federation and operates a federal Constitution. An important attribute of a Constitution is that there is a division of power between the centre or the Federal government, and the states. The powers and roles given to each of the governments are as defined and set out in the Constitution. None of the governments is allowed to step out of its assigned field. If it does, whatever it does outside its assigned field will be unconstitutional and will be declared null and void by the court.

The above notions of the court are to the fact that every arm has its own power, scope, extent and limitation to which it can act. Any act done by an arm outside what the Constitution has provided would amount to an oversight. In the case of *Ordu v.*

⁵⁸ *Inokoju v. Adeleke* (2007) 4 NWLR (Pt. 1025) 423 SC.

⁵⁹ *Amaechi v. INEC* (2007) Suit. No. SC 252/2007. Judgement delivered by Katsina-Alu, JSC. The Daily Independent, 08 November 2007.

⁶⁰ (2002) 15 NWLR (Pt. 791) 539.

⁶¹ (2005) 2 WRN 1 S.C

Elewa,⁶² the court said, ‘the word *oversight* simply means an unintentional failure to notice or do something’.

Black’s Law Dictionary,⁶³ ‘the theory of governmental power and functions whereby each branch of government has the ability to counter the actions of any other branch, so that no single branch can control the entire government’. Ojo⁶⁴ has his own opinion regarding check and balances, he said:

The Constitution conceded in many areas the fusion not only of powers but also of functionaries and functions. The need to integrate the dispersed powers into workable government was realized. While it entrenched separateness it insisted on interdependence, while it provided for autonomy, it deferred to reciprocity. In one’s view, the controversy about the doctrine of separation of powers has moved from the desirability or need for it to the technique for control of powers.

Flowing from the above facts, it is safe to assert that the President, in the exercise of his duties cannot declare war on any other country except with the approval by resolution of both Houses of the National Assembly sitting in a Joint Session as contained in section 5 (4) a of the 1999 Constitution, while sub-section 4 (b) of the same section further buttresses that no member of the Armed Forces shall be validly deployed for any combat duties or fight outside Nigeria. Similarly, section 12(1) of the Constitution provides that no treaty between Nigeria and another country shall have the force of law except to the extent to which such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly. Any treaty not ratified by the National Assembly is void⁶⁵ regardless of how sound it is made. It is correct to state that only when the agreement is domesticated by the National Assembly enacting the provisions thereof into law before it can become enforceable within the shores of Nigeria. As such, section 12 (2) of the Constitution stipulates that ‘The National Assembly may make laws for the Federation or any part thereof with respect to matters not included in the Exclusive Legislative List for the purpose of implementing a Treaty. In *Abacha & ors v. Fawehinmi*,⁶⁶ the position of the African Charter on Human and People’s right was in

⁶² (2018) 17 NWLR (Pt. 1469) 515.

⁶³ Bryan A Garner, *Black’s Law Dictionary* (11th Edn, Thomson West, St Paul, USA, 2019) 298.

⁶⁴ Abiola Ojo, *Constitutional Law and Military Rule in Nigeria*, (Evans Brothers Limited, 1987), 149. Also quoted in A.A. Borokini ‘The Doctrine of Separation of Powers and the 1999 Constitution’ in *Journal of Private and Commercial Law*, Faculty of Law, University of Ado-Ekiti, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State p. 147.

⁶⁵ *Abacha & ors v. Fawehinmi* (2000) LPELR-14(SC) Para C., 13-14.

⁶⁶ (2000) LPELR-14(SC) Para F., 47-48.

question before the Apex Court of Nigeria as a result of the arrest and detention of the Respondent by SSS operatives. The court held that:

It suffices to say that an international treaty entered into by the government of Nigeria does not become binding until enacted by the National Assembly. See section 12 (1) of the 1979 Constitution which provides that “no treaty between the Federation and any other country shall have the force of law except to which any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly (reenactment in section 12 (1) of the 1999 Constitution).before the National Assembly enacts any law, such law has no force of law as to make its provisions justifiable in our courts...

The position of the court reiterates the point that no treaty shall have a binding force in Nigeria if the National Assembly has not enacted it, regardless of how healthy such treaty is or how beneficial it be can. Although the President has the power to issue a Proclamation of a State of Emergency provided that such proclamation has been lawfully approved by the National Assembly within the time frame for which it is to be made. Consequently, section 305 (1) and (2) of the Constitution of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) provide thus:

- 1) Subject to the provisions of this Constitution, the President may by instrument published in the Official Gazette of the Government of the Federation issue a Proclamation of a state of emergency in the Federation or any part thereof.
- 2) The President shall immediately after the publication, transmit a copy of the Official Gazette of the Government of the Federation containing the proclamation including the details of the emergency to the President of the Senate and the Speaker of the House of Representatives, each of whom shall forthwith convene or arrange for a meeting of the House of which he is President or Speaker as the case may be to consider the situation and decide whether or not to pass a resolution approving the Proclamation.

Summarily, the above provisions is to the effect that one authority or arm of the government cannot work effectively without the other nor can it act alone as that will surely rock the boat of stability due to constitutional order or process.⁶⁷

⁶⁷ Chevron (Nig) Ltd v. Imo State House of Assembly & ors Para E-E. 56-57.

6. CONCLUSION

This study has looked into the arms of government, principle of separation of powers as provided for in the constitutional framework likewise analyzing the distribution of governmental powers amongst these arms as well as their differences and divergences.⁶⁸ The idea of this study in relation to the arms of government is to enlighten the doctrine that no single arm of government should wholly and solely be dependent in another arm. This study further explains that, no person should be exempt from prosecution as it tackles the aim of the rule of law linking the principles upheld in the case of *Ibrahim v. Osunde & ors.*⁶⁹ It reads thus:

The honored principle is that No one can or shall take advantage of his own wrong doing; the Maxim is "NULLUM COMMODUM CAPERE POTEST DE INJURIA SUA PROPRIA" EX TURPI CAUSA NON ORITUR ACTIO. Lord Widgery put this proposition in a glowing language when in *BUSWELL VS. GODWIN* (1971) 1 ALL E.R 421 he said and I quote: The proposition that a man will not be allowed to take advantage of his own wrong is no doubt a very salutary one and one which the Court would wish to endorse. Let me say that no polluted hand shall be allowed to touch the pure fountain of justice...

This judicial precedent narrates that justice must be served in order for any society to thrive. Apparently, it will be against the principle of justice for any person who does wrong or commits an act against the backdrop be exempted from any civil or criminal liabilities. Simply, no person should be placed above the law in any matter, be it trivial or serious in order to preserve the principle of 'equality before the law'.⁷⁰ However, some qualifications or modifications in view of the fact that some Acts of Parliament have given judicial and quasi-judicial powers to administrative adjudicatory bodies which are not part of regular court proceedings such as privileges and exemption from liability based on public policy.⁷¹

⁶⁸ S.4-6 of the 1999 Constitution.

⁶⁹ (2009) LPELR-1411(SC) Para E. 30-31.

⁷⁰ S.17 (1) and (2a) of the CFRN. A.V Dicey, *The Law of the Constitution*, London. 10th ed. p. 202. *Aoko v. Fagbemi* (1961) ANLR. *Tofi v. Uba* (1987) 2 NWLR (Pt. 62), p. 707 CA.

⁷¹ S.308 of the CFRN. *Keyamo v. Isha* (2000) NWLR (Pt. 680), p. 196 CA and *Tinubu v. IMB Securities PLC* (2001) 16 NWLR (Pt. 740), p. 670 SC.

7. Recommendation

The implication of this clause is that the Constitution should always be determined in such a way that it would construe the true intention and purpose of the grundnorm, as contained in the preamble of the Supreme law and public officers be brought to book if the need arises. Therefore, I submit that persons entitled to enjoy the immunity clause for the period of time in office as contained in the Constitution should not use the medium as a tool to exercise mala fide actions and impunity.